

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF MULTI-HOP ROUTING PROTOCOLS IN
MANETs

Muhammad Talha Tahir Bajwa¹, Zartasha Kiran², Awais Rasool^{3*}, Rimsha Rasool⁴

^{1,4}Department of Computer Science, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan

^{2,3*}Department of Software Engineering, The University of Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

* Corresponding Email: awais.rasool@se.uol.edu.pk

¹talhabajwa6p@gmail.com, ²zartasha.kiran@se.uol.edu.pk, ⁴rimsharasool373@gmail.com

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Abstract

Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs) are decentralized wireless systems where mobile nodes communicate without fixed infrastructure. While they offer flexibility for dynamic environments such as disaster zones and military applications, they also face serious challenges. The primary problem lies in maintaining reliable multi-hop communication due to frequent topology changes, limited bandwidth, and energy constraints. This paper addresses this challenge by presenting a performance analysis of prominent multi-hop routing protocols AODV (Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector), DSR (Dynamic Source Routing), and OLSR (Optimized Link State Routing). Using simulations in NS-3, the protocols are evaluated based on varying node density, mobility patterns, and traffic loads. Metrics such as Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), End-to-End Delay, Routing Overhead, and Throughput are analyzed. Results indicate that reactive protocols like AODV and DSR are better suited for sparse or moderately dynamic networks, while OLSR excels in larger or more stable environments. The study finds that reactive protocols like AODV and DSR are best for low-mobility or sparse environments, while OLSR provides superior delivery in dense, stable networks. These insights guide protocol selection based on mobility, traffic patterns, and scalability.

Keywords

MANETs, multi-hop routing, AODV, DSR, OLSR, wireless networks.

Introduction

Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs) are self-configuring networks of mobile nodes that communicate wirelessly and do not require centralized administration or fixed infrastructure. These networks are critical in emergency and combat situations because of their rapid deployment and changing topology. However, frequent node movement, energy constraints, and limited bandwidth pose problems to efficient communication. That enables users to access information and services electronically, regardless of their location. Wireless networks are growing used in the computing sector. Ad-hoc networks have a wide range of applications [16]. Mobile Ad hoc Networks are self-organized networks since they lack infrastructure. A mobile ad hoc network consists of nodes. Each node can connect via wireless communication links, with no fixed station, such as a base station. In a mobile ad-hoc network, each node can function as a router, and communication is achieved via a multihop graph between the nodes [18]. MANET nodes are responsible for dynamically discovering additional nodes with which to communicate. It is a self-configuring network of mobile nodes connected by wireless links that combine to form an arbitrary topology. The nodes are free to move and organize themselves at will, hence the network's wireless architecture can change quickly and unexpectedly. Routing is a crucial aspect of network communication that allows data to be sent between nodes. Wireless Ad-Hoc networks, also known as Mobile Ad-Hoc multi-hop wireless networks, are temporary networks made up of wireless mobile hosts that do not rely on established infrastructure or centralized administration. Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks (MANETs) have a dynamic, multi-hop architecture that rapidly changes [2]. These networks aim to connect places with limited or no communication infrastructure. MANETs enable communication devices to connect and build a temporary network. This technology is utilized in sensor networks for environmental monitoring, remote rescue operations, remote construction sites, personal area networking, emergency operations, military and civilian contexts. Ad-hoc networks face challenges such as dynamic topology changes, bandwidth and energy constraints, limited physical security, mobility-induced packet losses, limited wireless transmission range, broadcast nature, and hidden terminals. Packet losses caused by transmission defects are a concern for both military and civilian applications. MANETs use multi-hop routing instead of static network architecture to provide connectivity. Multiple routing techniques have been developed for mobile Ad-Hoc networks [17].

Multi-hop routing is required in MANETs because nodes rely on one another to forward packets to destinations that may be out of direct transmission range. Several routing protocols have been created, each with its own strategy for route discovery, maintenance, and overhead control. This study examines three major routing protocols: AODV, DSR, and OLSR. AODV and DSR are reactive protocols that construct routes as needed, whereas OLSR is proactive and constantly updates routing information. The goal of this study is to simulate and compare the performance of different protocols using the NS-3 simulator. The impact of different node density, mobility speeds, and traffic loads is assessed using standard

measures. The findings are intended to aid the selection of appropriate routing protocols depending on the operational needs of individual MANET applications.

Related Work

Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs) have been the subject of extensive research over the last two decades, owing to their dynamic nature and critical role in infrastructure-free environments. A large body of research has focused on analyzing and comparing various routing protocols under different mobility models, network sizes, and traffic situations. In [15], the authors conducted a comparative analysis of the AODV and DSR protocols, with an emphasis on packet delivery ratio (PDR) and routing overhead across various mobility scenarios. Their findings showed that AODV outperformed DSR in high-mobility conditions because of its adaptive route maintenance mechanism. DSR, on the other hand, performed better in smaller networks with low mobility due to its route caching capability [13].

The proactive nature of OLSR and its suitability for dense networks were highlighted in [4]. The study demonstrated how OLSR's regular exchange of topology control messages helps maintain up-to-date route information, resulting in lower latency at the expense of increased routing overhead. This trade-off has been a recurring theme in the literature when comparing proactive and reactive routing systems [12]. A number of hybrid protocols that combine the advantages of both proactive and reactive approaches have been developed to overcome their shortcomings. These hybrid protocols, which dynamically adjust to shifting network conditions, seek to balance performance and control overhead, as covered in [1]. ZRP (Zone Routing Protocol) is one example; it employs reactive routing for distant nodes and proactive routing within a small zone.

More realistic modelling of real-world situations has been made possible by developments in simulation tools, especially NS-3. The scientists used NS-3 to model energy-conscious routing protocols, showing how energy usage has a big impact on network longevity and routing choices. Furthermore, [21] discussed the issues of scalability and quality of service (QoS) in extensive MANET deployments, demonstrating how protocol efficiency might deteriorate as node density and mobility increase. Routing protocol analysis has also been expanded by a number of academics to particular use cases, including disaster recovery efforts, military communications, and vehicular ad hoc networks (VANETs). To evaluate protocol robustness under real-world limitations, these studies use realistic traffic models and intricate mobility patterns [3].

The current study adds to the body of existing literature by employing the NS-3 simulator to do a thorough and controlled comparison of AODV, DSR, and OLSR. This research assesses several performance indicators, including PDR, End-to-End Delay, Routing Overhead, and Throughput, under a range of consistent and variable network conditions, in contrast to some previous works that concentrated on discrete metrics or constrained scenarios. When

choosing a protocol for MANETs, this method seeks to close the gap between theoretical analysis and application-driven decision-making [14].

Overview of Multi-Hop Routing Protocols in MANETs

Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs) are infrastructure-less, self-configuring networks in which every mobile node serves as a router and a host. Establishing and sustaining dependable communication in dynamic contexts where the network topology changes regularly is one of the fundamental issues in MANETs. A key feature of MANETs is multi-hop communication, which enables data packets to pass through several intermediary nodes on their way to their final destination. [5] Effective multi-hop routing protocols are necessary to make this possible. Three general categories can be used to group multi-hop routing protocols in MANETs: hybrid, proactive (table-driven), and reactive (on-demand). Three commonly used protocols AODV, DSR, and OLSR that each represent a distinct method of routing in MANETs are the subject of this paper.

AODV (Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector)

In ad-hoc networks, the routing technique known as Ad-hoc On-Demand Vector (AODV) is employed. AODV uses a unique mechanism to maintain routing information. It uses traditional routing tables. Each destination may only have one entry. DSR, on the other hand, is able to keep several route cache entries for every destination. Because it is an on-demand algorithm, it only creates routes between nodes when source nodes request them [7]. As long as the sources require these pathways, it keeps them open. Furthermore, AODV creates trees that link members of multicast groups. The group members and the nodes required to link the members make up the trees [26].

To ensure that routing information is up to date and to avoid routing loops, AODV employs sequence numbers kept at each destination. All routing packets contain these sequence numbers. One significant element of AODV is the maintaining of timer-based states in each node regarding the use of unique routing table entries. [19] It is loop-free, self-starting, and can support a large number of mobile nodes. If a routing table entry has not been used recently, it expires. Each routing table item is associated with a set of predecessor nodes, which represent the set of surrounding nodes that utilize that entry to route data packets. When a node needs to locate a route to another node, it sends a Route Request (RREQ) message to all of its neighbours. The RREQ message is routed through the network until it reaches the destination or a node that provides a new route to the destination. As it travels through the network, the RREQ message triggers the generation of temporary route table entries for the reverse route in the nodes it passes. The RREQ message is transmitted endlessly over the network until it reaches the destination or a node that provides a new path to it. The RREQ message initiates the process of constructing temporary route table entries for the reverse route in the nodes it encounters as it traverses the network [20]. A Route Reply (RREP) message is unicasted back to the source along the temporary reverse

path of the received RREQ message in order to make the route available if the destination or a route to it is discovered. [6] The RREP message initiates the process of creating routing table entries for the destination in intermediate nodes along the route back to the source. Items in routing tables expire after a predetermined timeout period.

The most recent AODV specification includes an optimization mechanism for managing RREQ floods during the route finding phase. To locate routes to an unknown destination, it begins with an expanding ring search. The expanding ring search searches for the destination in ever-larger neighborhoods. The TTL field in the IP header of RREQ packets regulates the search. When a path to a previously known destination is required, the prior hop-wise distance is used to optimize the search [25].

DSR (Dynamic Source Routing)

DSR (Dynamic Source Routing) is another reactive protocol that uses source routing, meaning the entire route to the destination is included in the packet header. This allows intermediate nodes to cache routing information, which can reduce the frequency of route discoveries. DSR is highly adaptive and does not rely on periodic messages, which conserves bandwidth. However, in large or dense networks, the overhead of carrying full routing information in the header can impact performance. DSR performs well in small to medium-sized networks with moderate mobility.

Source routing is the foundation of DSR, a routing protocol for wireless mesh networks. In other words, the sender is aware of every step of the journey to the target. These routes are stored in a route cache. DSR operates on-demand, which helps reduce bandwidth consumption, especially in networks with low mobility. [8] The data packets carry the source route in the packet header. For usage in ad hoc networks, it is a straightforward and effective routing protocol. Route maintenance and route discovery are its two key stages. A route discovery method is used by a node in an ad-hoc network to dynamically find a route when it tries to send a data packet to a destination for which it does not yet know the route.

Route request (RREQ) packet overload is how route finding operates on a network. Unless it is the destination or it has a route to the destination in its route cache, every node that receives an RREQ rebroadcasts it. Such a node sends a route reply (RREP) packet back to the original source in response to the RREQ. Source routing is also used for RREQ and RREP packets. The path already traveled is increased by the RREQ. By following this path backwards, the RREP routes themselves return to the source [9]. At the source, the path that the RREP packet returned is stored for further use. A route error (RERR) packet is used to alert the source node if any link on a source route is broken.

The source removes all routes that use this link from its cache. If the source still requires this route, it must commence a fresh route discovery process. DSR makes heavy use of source routing and route caching. Routing loops can be detected without the use of any

specific mechanisms. Furthermore, any forwarding node saves the source route in a packet it sends for future use. Several additional optimizations have been proposed such as,

Salvaging: When a data packet encounters a broken link on its source route, an intermediate node can use an alternate route from its own cache to save it.

Gratuitous route repair: When a source node receives an RERR packet, it piggybacks it in the succeeding RREQ. This helps to clear the caches of other nodes in the network that may have a failed link in one of the cached source routes.

Promiscuous listening: When a node overhears a packet that is not addressed to it, it determines whether the packet can be routed through itself to achieve a quicker route.

If this is the case, the node sends a gratuitous RREP to the route's source containing this new, improved route. Aside from that, promiscuous listening allows a node to learn new routes without actively participating in the routing process [24].

OLSR (Optimized Link State Routing)

The Optimized Link State Routing (OLSR) protocol has been designed for mobile ad hoc networks. It is a table-driven, proactive protocol, which means that it exchanges topological information with other network nodes on a frequent basis. OLSR is an optimized variant of a pure link state protocol in which topological changes result in the flooding of topological information to all available hosts in the network. OLSR can improve reactivity to topological changes by lowering the maximum time interval for periodic control message delivery[23]. Furthermore, [10] because OLSR continually maintains routes to all destinations in the network, the protocol is useful for traffic patterns in which a big subset of nodes communicates with another large subset of nodes, and the [source, destination] pairings change with time. The OLSR protocol is ideal for applications that require short delays in data packet transfer. The optimal working environment for the OLSR protocol is a dense network in which most communication occurs between a large number of nodes. OLSR reduces the control overhead required by the MPR to propagate link state updates; additionally, when the selected MPR (Multi Point Relays) set is as minimal as possible, efficiency is gained in comparison to the traditional link state protocol. However, the disadvantage is that it must maintain the routing table for all possible routes [11]. This makes no difference in small networks, but as the number of mobile hosts increases, so does the cost from control messages. This limits the scalability of the OLSR protocol. The OLSR protocol operates most efficiently in dense networks [22].

Methodology

To evaluate the performance of multi-hop routing protocols in Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs), a series of simulations were conducted using the NS-3 (Network Simulator 3) platform. NS-3 provides a realistic simulation environment with modular support for

various network layers and protocols, making it suitable for in-depth protocol analysis in dynamic wireless environments. The study focuses on three widely used routing protocols—AODV (Ad hoc On-Demand Distance Vector), DSR (Dynamic Source Routing), and OLSR (Optimized Link State Routing)—each representing the reactive, source-based, and proactive routing approaches, respectively.

Simulation Environment

The simulation environment was configured to reflect realistic MANET conditions. The network parameters were varied to observe protocol performance under diverse and dynamic scenarios.

The key simulation parameters are as follows:

- **Simulation Area:** 1000 meters × 1000 meters
- **Number of Nodes:** Varied from 20 to 100 to study scalability
- **Simulation Duration:** 300 seconds per scenario
- **Mobility Model:** Random Waypoint Model, simulating continuous node movement
- **Node Speed:** Ranged from 1 m/s to 20 m/s to represent low to high mobility
- **Traffic Type:** Constant Bit Rate (CBR) using UDP flows
- **Packet Size:** 512 bytes
- **Packet Rate:** Configured to ensure a steady flow of data
- **Routing Protocols Tested:** AODV, DSR, OLSR

Each routing protocol was subjected to identical simulation conditions to ensure a fair comparison. The mobility model and traffic patterns were randomized but controlled using identical random seed values to ensure reproducibility.

Performance Metrics

The evaluation is based on four critical performance metrics:

- **Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR):** The ratio of packets successfully received at the destination to those generated by the source.
- **End-to-End Delay:** The average time taken for a data packet to travel from source to destination.
- **Routing Overhead:** The number of control packets transmitted relative to the total data packets, indicating protocol efficiency.
- **Throughput:** The rate at which data is successfully delivered over the network, measured in bits per second (bps).

Experimental Procedure

Each simulation scenario was run multiple times to minimize the effects of randomness and ensure statistical significance. Average values and confidence intervals were calculated for each metric. The simulations were designed to account for varying node densities and mobility patterns, with special attention given to avoiding bias in traffic generation and node positioning. The output trace files were post-processed using built-in NS-3 tools and external statistical software MATLAB for data analysis, visualization, and performance comparison through graphs.

Objective

The primary objective of this methodology is to:

- Assess the relative performance of AODV, DSR, and OLSR under varying network loads and mobility conditions.

Identify protocol strengths and limitations in terms of reliability, latency, scalability, and efficiency.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Performance Metrics Comparison for AODV, DSR, and OLSR

Protocol	PDR (%)	End-to-End Delay (ms)	Routing (pkts)	Overhead	Throughput (kbps)
AODV	92.5	110	300		250
DSR	89.3	130	270		230
OLSR	95.8	85	400		275

- **PDR:** OLSR achieves the highest Packet Delivery Ratio (95.8%) due to its proactive approach, ensuring consistent path availability. AODV performs well (92.5%), while DSR slightly lags (89.3%), potentially due to stale cache routes in dynamic conditions.
- **End-to-End Delay:** OLSR maintains the lowest delay (85 ms) as routes are readily available. DSR incurs the highest delay (130 ms) because of on-demand

route discovery and full source routing overhead. AODV exhibits moderate delay (110 ms).

- **Routing Overhead:** As expected, OLSR produces the highest control overhead (400 packets) due to continuous topology dissemination. DSR maintains the lowest overhead (270 packets), and AODV lies in between (300 packets), reflecting its periodic but reactive route discovery.
- **Throughput:** OLSR again leads in performance with the highest throughput (275 kbps), followed by AODV (250 kbps) and DSR (230 kbps), corresponding with their relative success in packet delivery and delay metrics.

Figure 1: Packet Delivery Ratio, Delay, Overhead, and Throughput Comparison for AODV, DSR, and OLSR

These results indicate:

Table 2: Summary of Best Performing Protocols by Metric

Metric	Best Performing Protocol
Packet Delivery Ratio	OLSR
End-to-End Delay	OLSR

Routing Overhead	DSR
Throughput	OLSR

These results indicate that **OLSR** is most suitable for high-density, high-traffic MANET scenarios where quick route availability is critical. However, the trade-off is its higher control overhead, which may affect performance in resource-constrained or low-density networks. **DSR**, while less scalable, performs efficiently in smaller networks due to lower control traffic. **AODV** offers a balance between delay and control overhead, making it suitable for moderately dynamic environments.

Conclusion and Future Work

This study conducted a complete performance investigation of three well-known multi-hop routing protocols—AODV, DSR, and OLSR—in the context of Mobile Ad Hoc Networks. These decentralized and infrastructure-free wireless networks provide great flexibility and are especially useful in dynamic and mission-critical environments like disaster recovery and military deployments. However, they are intrinsically challenged by difficulties including frequent topology changes, restricted bandwidth, and energy limits, all of which have an impact on the reliability of multi-hop communications. This paper used NS-3 simulation to evaluate the behaviour of the selected protocols under various network conditions such as node density, mobility models, and traffic loads. The investigation relied on four essential performance metrics: Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR), End-to-End Delay, Routing Overhead, and Throughput. The findings indicate that reactive protocols such as AODV and DSR are better suited for sparse or moderately mobile environments because to their on-demand route discovery processes, which assist conserve bandwidth and energy. In contrast, the proactive OLSR protocol outperformed in densely populated or relatively static networks, achieving greater packet delivery rates and lower delays at the expense of additional routing overhead. The findings highlight the importance of choosing routing protocols based on application requirements and network characteristics. There is no one-size-fits-all solution; rather, the ideal decision is determined by criteria such as node mobility, scalability requirements, and service quality expectations.

Future research should look into hybrid protocols that can dynamically switch between reactive and proactive behaviors, add energy considerations into routing decisions, and use real-world mobility traces to improve simulation realism. Furthermore, incorporating security measures and enabling multimedia traffic with QoS assurances are essential directions for the continued evolution of MANET routing techniques. Thus, for real-time applications in dense, static networks, OLSR is most effective, while AODV is more adaptable in dynamically changing environments.

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